

Mamadova Shafag Elif

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant
,Department of Therapeutik Dentistry

Quliyev Musa Elshad

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine Assistet
,Department of Therapeutik Dentistry

Kalbiyeva Nargiz Alibakhish

Department of Pediatrik Dentistry Assistant

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PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF THE USE OF THERMOPHILES IN ENDODONTICS.

Abstract:

The article is devoted to the clinical aspects of the use of hot gutta-percha on a carrier (thermophiles) in the daily practice of a dentist. An analysis of the features of using this technique in comparison with the method of lateral compaction of gutta-percha was carried out. At the preclinical stage, the apical permeability of the roots of teeth filled using these techniques was compared. The clinic treated caries complications in 878 teeth in 645 patients aged 18 to 75 years over a three-year period. The study found that there were no significant differences in the effectiveness of these techniques.

Key words: root canal filling, thermophiles, root filling.

The final stage of endodontic treatment is the hermetic filling of the main root canal and its additional branches and deltas available for sealing. The main task of root canal filling is to eliminate the possibility of microbes multiplying on the canal walls, depriving them of their habitat and, thanks to this, achieving a good treatment result [1,2]. Having prepared the canal for sealing, the dentist is faced with the choice of filling material. For more than 100 years, gutta-percha has been one of these sealants. There are more than a dozen methods for working gutta-percha in the canal alone. Each of them has advantages and disadvantages. A prerequisite for working with gutta-percha is the use of a sealer, which is designed to fill the spaces between the walls of the canal and gutta-percha, to obstruct microchannels, and in the case of lateral condensation, to glue gutta-percha pins. Since there is a risk of the sealer being released into the periapical space with any method of canal filling, it must meet quite a lot of requirements: be radiopaque, non-toxic, not affect regeneration processes, be plastic, fluid, stable in an aqueous environment, harden slowly, etc.[3, 4.5]. For two years now, after preparing root canals with ProTaper and Gt-file, we fill them with thermoplastic gutta-percha.

This method of filling canals is described in many textbooks and manuals, however, for the umpteenth time we are convinced of how right the great A.S. was. Pushkin, writing: "...and experience is the son of difficult mistakes...". Despite its apparent simplicity, filling with thermophiles can lead to complications (immediate and long-term). We bring to your attention an analysis of some experience of working with thermophiles. For the obturation of 220 root canals in the treatment of caries complications, we used thermophiles (Dentsplay) in combination with AN+ sealer, according to the manufacturer's method. The canals were prepared with ProTaper. X-ray control was carried out using a Trophy radiovisiograph. When assessing the complications of the treatment, we have traditionally identified 2 groups: immediate (pain after canal filling) and remote (presence of signs of chronic inflammation of

apical periodontitis). In order to monitor the results, we conducted repeated radiovisiography in 84 root canals 6–12 months after treatment. The criteria for the quality of canal filling were considered to be obturation along the entire length, the absence of voids in the canal, and filling of the delta. We noted so-called post-filling pain after treatment of 14 root canals (6.36%), regardless of the clinical diagnosis. Analyzing the radiovisiograms, we noted in 9 cases of them the removal of the filling material beyond the apex of the tooth root. Considering that Thermafil was installed in the canal to the working length, it can be assumed that there was a flowable sealer outside the canal. The periodontal reaction in the form of constant pain or pain when biting was, in general, not very pronounced and disappeared on its own after 3–4 days. However, in two cases the pain was intense and was accompanied by swelling along the transitional fold. At the same time, the amount of sealer in the periapical tissues was insignificant. Since no radiological changes were noted before treatment, this reaction of apical periodontal tissue can be explained by severe irritation with the sealer, both mechanical and chemical. Mechanical trauma to the periodontium during root canal preparation is also possible[6]. Why does the filling material end up outside the root apex when working with Thermafil? Let's try to understand the reasons for this situation. First of all, due to non-compliance with the ProTaper root canal preparation technique. This includes incorrect measurement of the working length of the canal, especially with external resorption of the tooth root, and arbitrary selection of instruments in violation of the sequence of their work. The second reason, in our opinion, is the excessive introduction of sealer into the canal. Many dentists, out of habit, use a canal filler at this stage. In this case, subsequent injection of Thermafil will inevitably lead to the sealer being pushed out of the channel. Do not neglect the advice of the creators of the method. It is enough just to lubricate the canal walls with sealer, using an ordinary gutta-percha pin of a suitable size. Excessive pressure on the carrier of heated gutta-percha can also contribute to the removal of the sealer into the

periapical space. Thermafil should be easily inserted into the canal, reaching the working length fixed on it without any pressure. This can only happen if the channel diameter is pre-calibrated. Otherwise, it is possible to remove not only the sealer, but also the flowing, heated gutta-percha. There are no small details in dentistry. Failure to perform any seemingly insignificant manipulation can affect the outcome of treatment. More than 90 long-term complications of endodontic treatment are associated with incomplete obturation of the root canal. Therefore, the preliminary probing stage is so important in order to search for all possible root canals in the tooth. West wrote in 1975: "In 100% of cases of complications in endodontics, there is at least one unsealed portal of infection into the periodontium." Thermoplastic gutta-percha, due to its properties and subject to high-quality preparation of the root canal, removal of the smear layer from its walls and prolonged rinsing, makes it possible to obturate not only the main trunk of the canal, but also its lateral branches and even the delta in the area of the root apex, which ensures success in treatment. During a repeated examination of 84 root canals (49 after treatment of apical periodontitis and 35 after pulpitis), not a single case of clinically manifested periodontitis was noted. Percussion of all teeth was painless, there were no changes in the mucous membrane of the gums in the area of the apex of the tooth root. Filling the root canals with Thermafil resulted in a reduction or disappearance of foci of destruction in periapical tissues (Fig. 1–2, b). However, in 6 cases (12.2%) with external resorption of the root apex and removal of the sealer, no change in the source of inflammation was observed radiographically. At the same time, there were no traces of sealer in the periodontium. It is quite difficult to unambiguously assess the cause of this periodontal condition. There was probably some undetected channel, or a more detailed examination of the patient is required. After treatment of pulpitis, we did not notice any changes in the periodontium after 6–12 months (Fig. 3). Of the 28 cases of filling material being removed beyond the root, in 19 (67.85%) there was no presence of sealer in the periodontium, as well as signs of bone tissue inflammation. In 9 cases, the filling material was identified, but signs of inflammation were either absent or the focus of destruction decreased in size (Fig. 4). In all cases of filling with Thermafil, after 6–12 months, the filling density of the canal was maintained throughout the entire length, and there were no voids. In 45 (23%) cases, filled lateral canals are visible (Fig. 5), mainly in single-rooted teeth or root deltas. Using thermophiles in

canals of varying degrees of curvature, we were convinced that the opinion of our colleagues who have more experience working with them is absolutely correct: today thermofils are unsurpassed systems for reliable obturation of long and curved canals (Fig. 6, 7).

Conclusion.

The possibilities of modern endodontics give the doctor the right to choose the most effective methods and means of root canal treatment. Rotary instruments and thermophiles are one of them. By following the technology of working with them, you can achieve optimal results and avoid "unpleasant surprises."

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